

BUILDING SUSTAINABLE CITIES TO ADDRESS URBAN SPRAWL: A REFLECTIVE ANALYSIS TOWARDS ACHIEVING SDGs

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Abstract

The paper aims to evaluate the prospects of building a sustainable city to address urban sprawl in order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11. This paper focuses on SDG 11, which is concerned with making sustainable cities and communities. Its objective is to make cities and other populated areas more inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable in the long run. Examining some of the problems that impede the SDGs from being accomplished, urbanisation emerges as one of the most significant human endeavours, affecting the standard of urban living and its long-term development in most developing countries. In developing countries, many cities have been burdened with a new normal and culture of growth, driven by urban sprawl, which has led to the sustainable city strategy gaining popularity in recent years. Urbanisation is increasing at an unprecedented rate in many developing countries, threatening the achievement of SDGs due to the proliferation of urban sprawl. Currently, urban areas are home to over 50 % of the world's population. It is projected, that by 2045 urban areas will be home to more 6 billion people. These have placed severe constraints on local governments, who should be developing sustainable cities and communities in response to urban development to fulfil SDG 11. This makes it impossible to achieve SDG 11 by the projected deadline of 2030. This paper argues that without fundamentally changing how cities are built, developed and populated, sustainability in urban areas cannot be realised. This paper suggests that adequate and ready policy and legislative frameworks are needed to promote sustainable development and prevent urban sprawl in cities.

Keywords: Urban sprawl, Sustainable city, SDG 11, Urbanisation, Cities

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1. Introduction

Cities have evolved into important catalysts for changes in global socioeconomics, politics, and spatial that extend well beyond the boundaries of urbanised areas. The ratification of SDG 11, which aims to make cities and human settlements more inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable, acknowledges the transformative power of urban sprawl and its results [1]. According to Zhang et al. [2], by 2050, it is predicted, that 70 % of the world's population would live in cities. However, the rate of urbanisation, coupled with the increasing rates of unemployment, paint a blurry picture in the quest to address urban sprawl in developing countries. This explicitly demonstrates that the mushrooming of sprawl in cities is still to prolong and proliferate. Today, urban sprawl is the primary factor driving city growth and development, not only in African countries but throughout the world, especially in developing countries. Urban sprawl is becoming more and more prevalent, which results in a loss of biodiversity, increased government expenditures, climate change, and spatial complexity [2, 3]. Urban sprawl has been shown to frequently have a variety of negative effects, such as the inefficient use of land resources, rural outmigration, slums and informal housing in cities, heavy traffic and pollution, the disappearance of public spaces, deteriorated inner-city neighbourhoods, and public health issues [2–5].

In addressing issues of urban sprawl, the United Nations (UN) has established several indicators to evaluate how urban sprawl has affected land resources. The UN established 17 SDGs and 169 specific targets for changing the world in 2015. Amongst the SDGs, Goal 11 emphasises the significance of “making cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable” [1, 6]. The unprecedented rate of urbanisation, coupled with increasing urban unemployment and competition for land research, paint a blurry picture of the attainment of a safe and inclusive city that is environmentally safe. However, many people are located in urban areas, but the challenges of infrastructure development, service delivery provision, and underdeveloped settlement continue to exclude them. In this regard, urban sprawl has remained a dominant phenomenon in terms of sustainable city planning and development [7]. Many local governments across the world are overwhelmed by the increasing number of people in the city to provide basic resources to them [2]. As a result, achieving the SDGs by 2030 appears both impractical and feasible.

Zhang et al. [2] postulate that urban sprawl has been mainly driven by urbanisation for decades. The challenges of sustainable development as a result of sprawl are thus experienced more in many developing countries and urban communities, especially in the hotspot cities, which are urbanising quickly [7]. As many people are migrating to cities, it means more land occupation is needed; some urban land is occupied illegally without formal directives. These have added much burden and crippled the municipal budget. Multiple studies have revealed that many cities are increasingly having problems with issues, such as high poverty and unemployment rate, water and sanitation, spatial vulnerabilities and inefficiencies, etc [3, 7, 8]. Against this background, this paper notionally examines the prospects of building a sustainable city in the context of urban sprawl to achieve the SDGs. The paper grounds its premise on SDG 11, which is about creating sustainable cities and communities. Its goal is to make cities and communities more inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable in the future. Furthermore, a special emphasis is placed on the conceptualisation of a sustainable city. The challenges facing urban planning; the interrelationship between SDGs and urban sprawl; and the prospects for building sustainable cities. This paper aims to evaluate the prospects of building a sustainable city to address urban sprawl to help South Africa achieve the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11.

1. 1. Conceptualising sustainable city

The concept “sustainable city” is being reinterpreted by a growing body of scholarship. Clark [9] defines a sustainable city as a specific form of an urban area that wisely utilises natural and technological resources to meet the requirements of its population. According to Moen [10], the process of creating a sustainable city is all about innovation and transformation. According to Cohen and Dong [11], a “sustainable city” is one that can ensure that all its residents can meet their own needs without jeopardising the health of the environment or other people’s quality of life, now or in the future. Sustainable cities have an environment that is suited for human settlement, while not jeopardising the stability of future generations of citizens. These are cities that can balance their social, economic, and environmental needs [9]. The concept of a sustainable city stems from the ideology of sustainable development, with goals to establish a human settlement that does not destroy the natural environment and planet [9, 12]. MacDonald et al. [12] claim that the fundamental of a sustainable city pushes for growth that does not jeopardise future generations’ needs at the expense of current generations. A sustainable city, also known as a self-sustaining city, refers to city designs that minimise environmental effects, while considering long-term sustainability [12]. A city is sustainable if it can apply and produce its development model, self-governance approach, sustainable growth, resilience, efficiency, and justice [6].

Again, a sustainable city adheres to strict standards and guarantees that its residents enjoy the same rights as those who live outside, including access to education and health care [6]. As a result, citizen movement in the city must be as efficient as possible, while minimising the use of harmful fuels and the expense of power [13]. According to Barthel et al. [13], a sustainable city requires efficient urban transportation networks that reduce the need for personal automobiles and are effective in their large mechanisms (subway, buses, trains, etc). Effective resource management is required for cities to thrive in a way that protects green space and maintains a certain balance with rural areas [13]. It must inform its residents on how to reduce pollution, conserve energy,

reuse products that do not need to be replaced, and recycle garbage that should not be mixed with liquid or biodegradable waste [9]. For example, the City of London in the United Kingdom, Copenhagen in Denmark, and Lund in Sweden have been named the most sustainable cities in the world for their efforts to combat climate change and transition their municipalities to a more sustainable future. San Francisco, California, in the United States, is also regarded as the most sustainable city in the world, with a zero-waste strategy. According to Al-Gindy [14], the concept of sustainability and sustainable city development improves awareness of resource production and usage in transportation, business, education, and investments, as well as industrial districts. Al-Gindy [14] assert that the sustainable city concept collaborates with smart cities to improve environmental awareness about the usage of natural resources.

The concept of a “sustainable city” is problematic and impracticable in many developing countries, especially on the African continent. Given that most areas are rural, many cities on the continent are battling a variety of problems, primarily “urbanisation” [11]. Urbanisation on the African continent primarily affects cities due to immigration and emigration. These have a significant impact on the budget of government, especially when funding for sustainable city development is projected. Urban sprawl and other challenges, brought about by the phenomenon of urbanisation, have changed the way that urban land is managed, and the culture of sustainable urban planning has been affected [2]. In this regard, achieving the goal of a sustainable city in South Africa cannot be done overnight; rather, it requires the establishment of a readiness law and policy framework, retrofitting and redevelopment, resource redirection, and exceptionally good administration in urban government. It takes a lot of effort to extract and establish a strategic plan to maximise already-available resources, so that these resources can be used to build intelligent systems that provide people with vital infrastructure [13–15].

1. 2. Challenges facing urban planning

The global urban population is currently raising with the largest increase taking place in developing countries [8, 16, 17]. Many of the developing develop under the auspices of the colonial era. In many countries, their planning is still informed by colonial relics. Therefore, the countries’ urban planning challenges are frequently considered distinctive, which shows a state of a physically fractured urban environment [17–20]. Nevertheless, the sustainability problems that plague its cities demonstrate a growing range of issues that are common to many other fast-growing urban areas. Colonial relics in many countries influence urban development and spatial planning. Urban planning was therefore seen as a means of promoting sustainable urban growth and achieving well-being in urban societies [21–24]. Deconstructing issues, related to socioeconomic and environmental impacts in urban areas, was among the main aims of all strategic planning [24]. In addition, urban planning is linked to issues of legislative and policy frameworks that are not up to date with the most major challenges in urban communities (i. e., urbanisation, urban sprawl, etc.). Urban planning continues to be dominated and naturalised by the concerns of urbanisation and sprawl, surpassing the municipal’s initial objectives and resource priorities [3, 8, 17].

The country’s increasing urbanisation, combined with global issues, such as climate change, urban sprawl, water scarcity, environmental degradation, economic restructuring, and social exclusion, necessitates a closer examination of the future of cities by urban development planners [25]. As cities seek to meet the SDGs by 2030, humankind finds itself in a precarious situation, as human activities endanger the very support systems that are critical to human health and even survival [8]. Climate change, political uncertainty, economic disinvestment, and growing populations are some of the urban planning issues that cities have to deal with [8] [26]. According to Vaidya and Chatterjee [6], environmentally harmful technologies are the main factor contributing to inefficient urban planning in urban settings, while environmentally sustainable technologies are a key tool for producing effective urban planning. Sometimes a lack of awareness of spatial fragmentation and its effects on urban life leads to policies that are inadequate to address the problems facing urban areas [6, 26].

1. 3. SDGs and urban sprawls

Urban sprawl is one of the main effects of changes, brought on by population growth in urban centres [4]. Even though urban sprawl is commonly defined as “uncontrollable growth in

many housings, commercial development, and roads over large expanses of land, with little concern for planning in urban areas” [27], it has been defined differently by different scholars to reflect the purpose of their respective studies. The unprecedented rate of urban sprawl, which is mostly visible in cities within countries, is now thought to be principally caused by the growing global urban population. Urban sprawl occurs when a city’s population growth exceeds its capacity to sustain amenities, such as health care, schools, and recreation in addition to essential utilities including transportation, water, sewage, and housing [4, 5]. Due to the enormous increase in urbanisation levels in many countries around the world, the achievement of sustainable cities, as outlined in SDG 11, has come under scrutiny and is a controversial subject for scholars in many countries [4]. Sustainable cities are being redefined by a growing body of knowledge. Cities are no longer seen as sites where traditional culture ends in this environment. So, it was expected, that one of the 17 SDGs featured a goal specifically for cities.

Although the term “sustainable” has a wide range of applications, SDG 11’s supplemental targets provide it with a very particular framework for cities and urban areas. The 2030 aims cover topics, including housing, protecting cultural and natural resources, reducing catastrophe risk, building resilience, providing services, utilising resources efficiently, mobility, and development planning. The goals are important and relevant, but it is unclear whether they can be achieved, given the short amount of time available [1, 6]. Although it is stated in the agenda, that the continent will accelerate the implementation of its program of action to provide opportunities for all Africans to have decent and affordable housing in clean, secure, and well-planned environments, Nash et al. [7] criticise SDG 11’s overarching aspirations for failing to speak directly to urbanisation or cities, even though it is stated, that the continent will improve the livelihoods of the large percentage of people working and living in slums and informal settlements. Urban sprawl has been a bigger concern affecting many cities in developing countries; and as a result, it delayed the agenda of realising nationally set SDGs, especially when tracking the success and the lack therefore in the country thus far. Most urban or city development planning policies and legislative frameworks are not clear about integrating sustainable cities and urban sprawl [2, 7].

1. 4. Prospects for building a sustainable city

All urban problems, whether they be spatial, social, or economic, are seen to be resolved by the creation of sustainable cities. The concept of sustainable cities has received considerable acceptance globally, where it is seen as a crucial strategy for modernising and revitalising cities there in a sustainable way. As a result, the sustainable city is transformed into an adaptive idea that is applied by several catalysts at various geographic scales [26]. However, considering the burning issues that result in unsustainable cities due to the unprecedented and uncontrolled urbanisation of developing countries, it is paramount important to adopt and fast-track the concept of sustainable city development. In achieving the goal of a sustainable city, devoted to SDG 11, it must be considered, that urban planning and technology are the main domains and have a pivotal role in the realisation of sustainable cities [8]. The environment, basic infrastructure, and public health are coming under growing strain from rapid urbanisation, urban expansion and unsustainable consumption patterns [28]. Making cities sustainable would therefore require the development of commercial opportunities, secure and affordable housing, and resilient societies and economies [26]. It should involve funding public transit, creating green public spaces, and improving urban planning and management in ways that are inclusive and participatory [26, 28]. The building and development of sustainable cities in South Africa ought to be guided by the theories of green development, environmental friendliness, and fair development as a result of advances in science and technology, just like in China.

In the fight to stop global climate change, sustainable cities are becoming increasingly important. SDG 11 (sustainable cities and communities), calls for building beneficial economic, social, and environmental links between urban, peri-urban and rural areas [28]. More cities and human settlements adopting and implementing integrated policies and strategies for diversity, resource efficiency, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and catastrophe resilience may be advantageous for achieving more sustainable cities [26]. In this context, developing sustainable cities will help with putting into practice sustainable practices, such as making it simple to get around without a car, installing charging stations, granting access to public amenities

and green spaces, enhancing water conservation and wastewater management, promoting urban farming, and using green architecture. These will enable the countries to develop several programs for sustainable cities, eco-cities, low-carbon, liveable, resilient, sanitary and circular economy cities [28]. Promoting sustainable cities is essential, since it is predicted, that 70 % of the world's population will live in cities by 2050 [2, 28]. Due to rapid urbanisation, particularly the allocation of land, water, housing, infrastructure, and basic public services, is under a considerable deal of strain in developing countries.

The aim of the research was to evaluate the prospects of building a sustainable city to address urban sprawl in order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11.

2. Materials and Methods

This paper used qualitative desktop-based research methodology to gather information about the prospects of building a sustainable city in the setting of urban sprawl in cities to accomplish the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11. The desktop-based research in this paper was primarily concerned with gathering data from existing or secondary sources. The paper used World Bank as a source of secondary data regarding the state of the cities. In comparison to fieldwork, it is a low-cost research methodology. Information for this paper was collected from secondary sources, such as journals, books, the internet, and organisational websites. These sources were used with caution to ensure and maintain their validity, reliability and representativeness.

3. Results

Currently, some 56 % of the world's population, which accounts for 4.4 billion inhabitants, live in cities. World Bank has projected that over 6 billion inhabitants will be living in cities by the year 2045. This trend is expected to continue, with the urban population more than doubling its current size by 2050, at which point nearly 7 of 10 people will live in cities. However, the speed and scale of urbanization globally, especially in developing countries, brings challenges, such as *inter alia* meet accelerated demand for affordable housing, viable infrastructure, including transport systems, basic services delivery, and unemployment. This is for the nearly 1 billion urban poor who continue to live in informal settlements to be near opportunities. Rising conflicts contribute to pressure on cities as 50 % of forcibly displaced people live in urban areas. Once a city is built, its physical form and land use patterns can be locked in for generations, leading to unsustainable sprawl. The expansion of urban land consumption outpaces population growth by as much as 50 %, which is expected to add 1.2 million km² of new urban built-up area to the world by 2030. Therefore, such sprawl puts pressure on land and natural resources, resulting in undesirable outcomes; cities represent two-thirds of global energy consumption and account for more than 70 % of greenhouse gas emissions. Building cities that “work”, which are green, resilient and inclusive, requires intensive policy coordination and investment choices. Nearly one billion urban poor still live in slums and informal settlements, mostly in Asia, Africa, and Latin America, and are often excluded from access to affordable housing, good-quality basic services, and better jobs.

4. Discussion

The current rate of urbanisation and the increasing rates of urban sprawl formation post a deleterious effect on the sustainability of the city. Many people in the cities are forced to reside in unplanned and illegal land in order to access the city [9]. The inability of the local government to house and service the increasing urban population makes it difficult for the city to achieve a sustainable city. Urban sprawl has resulted in challenges, such as a decline in available productive land, a reduction in green spaces and a quality of services [4, 7]. Therefore, the proliferation of urban sprawl in developing countries makes it difficult for these to achieve SDG 11. Furthermore, cities continue to be plagued with an increasing number of the urban poor population residing in unsafe and poorly serviced settlements. According to World Bank, the organisation is working with the private sector, governments, civil society, and other partners to build inclusive, resilient, and sustainable cities and communities for all worldwide – and to help create competitive economies that provide new kinds of jobs, especially for the urban poor. With the increasing levels of urban population, coupled with the inability of local government to plan and manage this process, the attainment of SDG 11 will never be achieved.

Limitations of the study and prospects for further research is based on the fact the paper is purely theoretical and based on secondary data. The prospects vary from country to country or region to region. Thus, it may not be possible to generalise the findings to the world as a whole. Therefore, the scope of future research can be expanded by taking a global perspective and delving deeper into the prospects of creating sustainable cities to combat urban sprawl.

5. Conclusion

The uncontrollable expansion of human settlements in cities has resulted from a rapidly growing population. This has left local governments with no choice but to adopt and integrate their urban development plans with the recent urban sprawl conundrums within cities. This paper suggests that the degree of urban sprawl and how city spaces are planned and structured will both have a significant impact on whether the SDGs are achieved. The paper suggests that to improve sustainable development and combat urban sprawl in cities, appropriate and ready legal and policy frameworks are required. The paper further opines that urban sprawl has become a new norm, which has to be featured in sustainable city planning and policy frameworks, considering that the level of development is still a bigger issue in the country, especially in rural communities. The study also makes the case that cities should prepare for a new wave of urban sprawl that is likely to occur in the years to come. In this regard, developing a sustainable city within the context of urban sprawl would be a crucial strategy for countries to achieve SDG 11. Again, to successfully build sustainable cities, urban planning ought to be inclusive, sensitive to community needs, and based on participatory practices that encourage the engagement of disadvantaged people. Moreover, the paper recommends retrofitting and redevelopment of urban areas. In this way, the attainment of the set SDGs, particularly Goal 11, can be practicable and feasible in 2030.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest concerning this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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